

Appendix – Contingency Coding Categorization

The following table documents the categorization phase of our qualitative analysis. After identifying negatively valenced text units and inductive coding, we group them into thematically coherent categories. The table shows how initial labels were grouped, reviewed, and either retained as negative contingencies or excluded based on predefined criteria. Expressly, codes were excluded if they were (i) positively framed, (ii) fully controllable by the focal organization, or (iii) overlapping with well-established critical success factors (CSFs) such as those summarized by Mamudu et al. (2022). Both authors reviewed each retained contingency for contextual relevance and structural impact. The column 'Group Name' represents intermediate themes that support the formation of the broader 'Final Negative Contingency'.

Initial Code	Group name	Final negative contingency	Include/Exclude	Rationale
Degree of control	Global Collaboration	Distributed Development Team	Include	Coordination challenges, time zone, and communication issues are not fully controlled by the focal firm.
Create Global Measurement KPI				
International Distributed Development Team				
Define Coverage of the PM	Expectation Misalignment	Result Expectation	Include	Mismatch between expected and actual outcomes; affects perceived PM value
Understanding Business Need				
No Global Measurement Standard				
Data Privacy	Data Privacy	Data Privacy	Include	Legal or regulatory limitations not easily bypassed
Problem of IOT Data	IOT Data Complexity	IOT Data	Include	Data format issues and technical limitations in sensor-based data
No Data Translation				
Visualization of Data and Performance	Lack of Action and Improvement after PM Result	Insight-Improvement Disconnection	Include	Challenges in translating insights into actionable process change
Combine Analysis with Action				
Hackaton Format for Use Case Identification				
Performance Measurement Challenge				
Reporting Use Case				
Sharing Use Case Story	Knowledge Diffusion (Localize the solution)	Sharing Success Story	Include	PM value realization is not shared or localized effectively
Sharing Success Story				

Initial Code	Group name	Final negative contingency	Include/Exclude	Rationale			
Ownership of the Process	Ownership of the benefit	Organizational Alignment	Include	PM uptake may fail when those responsible for change lack clarity on their role and don't perceive a direct benefit from acting on insights. Alignment is missing not in structure, but in perceived accountability.			
Center of Excellence Adaptation							
Cross-Functional Team							
Create a Centre of Excellence							
Vendor Engagement							
Pre and After Service Care	Undocumented Work	Hidden Task	Include	Activities not visible in logs; reduce model completeness, request rework			
Hidden Task	Architecture Integration Choice	Architecture Integration Choice	Include	Structural or legacy barriers affecting PM deployment or growth impact			
Manage System Integration							
Growth Challenge							
Data Integration	Data		Exclude	General CSFs: challenging to position as contingent blockers			
Data							
Data Coverage							
Data Handling							
Data Integrity Challenge							
Integrate Machine Learning					Tech Optionality	Exclude	Within the organizational option to add or use the technology
License Procurement					Operational Planning	Exclude	Within the control of management, a common CSF issue
Resource Allocation							
Change Management							
Top Management Support					Implementation Strategy	Exclude	Within the control of management, common CSF
New Players Disrupt the Market	Positive Impact	Exclude	More positive reasons that have a positive impact, not negative				
HR Strategy	Expertise Alignment	Exclude	Fully controllable by the firm; part of enablement, not contingency				
Training Session							
Communication	Collaboration Challenge	Exclude	General CSFs: challenging to position as contingent blockers				
Governance							
Create Initiative Regarding Carbon Foot Print	Sustainability Framing	Exclude	Vision-level input, not process-specific contingency				